

Amidomethylation with 3,5-Dibromosalicylamide¹ : Part IV

GURU BACHAN SINGH, V. K. VIJAN, (MISS) ARUNA JETLY, V. K. CHHABRA and WAZIR MOHAMAD

Department of Pharmaceutics, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 5

Manuscript received 1 November 1971; revised 22 June 1972; accepted 7 May 1973

A few amidomethylations with *N*-hydroxymethyl 3,5-dibromosalicylamide and compounds containing a hydrogen of pronounced reactivity have been carried out employing Einhorn/Tscherniac procedure with a view to study their antimycotic activity and antibacterial activity.

SOME of the halogen derivatives² of *n*-substituted salicylamide like 4-chloro-*n*-butylsalicylamide, 3,5-dibromo-2',4'-dichlorosalicylanilide, 3,5,2',4'-tetrachlorosalicylanilide and 5-bromo-4'-chlorosalicylanilide have won importance as antimycotic drugs. It was therefore thought of interest to prepare some amidomethylation products of 3,5-dibromosalicylamide and to study their antimycotic activity.

Amidomethylation^{3,4} was carried out by condensing equimolecular quantities (0.01-0.05*M*) of the *N*-hydroxymethyl 3,5-dibromosalicylamide and the compound containing reactive hydrogen in acid medium. It could also be prepared by condensing the *N*-hydroxymethyl compound of the reactive component, after isolation or *in situ* with 3,5-dibromosalicylamide.

component/or the greater the electrophilic potential of the *N*-methylol compound the greater is the facility and ease of amidomethylation.

Experimental

N-Hydroxymethyl 3,5-dibromosalicylamide : 3,5-dibromosalicylamide (29.5 g., 0.1*M*) was warmed with 38% formaldehyde solution (25 ml., 0.12*M*) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4.5 g in 60 ml. water) till a clear solution was obtained. On cooling and neutralising with dilute hydrochloric acid, the crystals of *N*-hydroxymethyl-3,5-dibromosalicylamide separated out. Yield : 20 g (55%), m.p. 148°-50°. It gives positive Tollen's test. Found, N : 5.85, Br₂ : 70.97, C₈H₇Br₂N₃O requires : N : 6.20, Br₂ : 71.42.

As already observed in the case of 3,5-dibromosalicylamide⁵ and 3,5-dichlorosalicylamide⁵ that the introduction of Br or Cl atoms in the molecule of salicylamide facilitates aminoalkylation, the same holds good in their amidomethylation condensation. However, compared to aminoalkylation the amidomethylation requires a stronger acid catalyst to transform the *N*-hydroxymethylcarboxamide into an acylaminomethyl carbonium-immonium ion ($R-CO-NH-CH_2^+ \leftrightarrow R-CO-NH^+ = CH_2$), which eventually condenses with the carbanion, furnished by the reactive hydrogen component to yield the desired amidomethylation product. The greater the nucleophilic potential of the reactive hydrogen

Amidomethylation reactions were carried out either by Einhorn^{3,4} or Tscherniac^{3,4} procedure.

*Einhorn Procedure*⁶ : The compound containing reactive hydrogen atom (0.02*M*) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of ethanol (10-20 ml); and to this solution was added *N*-hydroxymethyl 3,5-dibromosalicylamide (6.5 g, 0.02*M*) in small portions with shaking. The reaction mixture was warmed, if necessary, to effect a clear solution. After adding conc. hydrochloric acid (1-2 ml), the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2-3 hr. on the water-bath. In most of the cases the amidomethylated product separated on cooling in ice, while in other cases the

TABLE 1. PRODUCTS OF AMIDOMETHYLATION WITH 3,5-DIBROMOSALICYLAMIDE AND DIFFERENT COMPOUNDS CONTAINING ACTIVE HYDROGEN

Sl. No.	Name of the Compound	Molecular formula	M.P.* °C	% Yield	% Nitrogen†		% Bromine‡	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	3-(3:5-dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-salicylic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Br ₂ NO ₅	180-82	72.0	2.96	3.10	35.70	36.18
2.	Methylene-bis-3,5-dibromosalicylamide	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	182-84	95.0	4.20	4.65	54.17	54.81
3.	N-salicylamidomethyl-3,5-dibromosalicylamide	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	110-12	79.0	5.85	6.30	35.72	36.04
4.	N-Benzamidomethyl-3,5-dibromosalicylamide	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	114-16	60.0	6.13	6.54	37.35	37.73
5.	N-Nicotinamidomethyl-3,5-dibromosalicylamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₃	126-28	73.0	9.25	9.79	36.85	37.29
6.	1-(3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-pyrrolidin 2:4 dione	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	122-24	81.0	6.39	6.89	36.80	37.27
7.	3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-thymol (3-hydroxy-4-isopropyl-toluene)	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ Br ₂ NO ₃	118-20	50.0	2.68	3.06	34.63	35.01
8.	N-(3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-sulphonamid	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₄ S	174-76	65.0	8.32	8.76	32.95	33.40
9.	4-(3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-1-phenyl-2,3-dimethyl-5-pyrazolon	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₃	118-20	62.0	7.96	8.46	31.86	32.23
10.	α-3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-β-naphthol	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ Br ₂ NO ₃	90-92	72.0	2.73	3.10	37.05	37.47
11.	N-3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-saccharin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	100-02	65.0	5.33	5.90	31.67	32.06
12.	N-3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-phthalimide	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	185(Dec.)	55.0	5.71	6.14	34.85	35.24
13.	3-(3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-benzoic acid (meta)	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	194-95	50.0	6.10	6.52	36.73	37.27
14.	3-(3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-p-cresol	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ Br ₂ NO ₃	201-02	46.0	2.86	3.30	37.58	38.40
15.	2-(3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-m-cresol	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ Br ₂ NO ₃	206-08	48.0	2.89	3.30	37.36	38.40
16.	3-(3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-p-nitrophenol	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄	186-8	69.0	6.01	6.20	34.92	35.60
17.	3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-oxamide	C ₁₀ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₄	275-77	56.0	10.38	10.60	37.96	39.30
18.	3-(3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-benzimidazole	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂	196-98	65.0	9.79	9.90	36.75	37.50
19.	3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-acetamide	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	196-97	68.0	7.38	7.60	42.23	43.40
20.	3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-chloroacetamide	C ₁₀ H ₉ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₃	140-41	58.0	6.95	7.01	—	—
21.	3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂	203-04	41.0	5.78	6.19	34.68	35.44
22.	3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-carbamide	C ₉ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₃	240-41	71.0	11.23	11.44	42.89	43.59
23.	3,5-Dibromosalicylamidomethyl-phenylacetamide	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₃	223-25	45.0	5.89	6.30	35.05	36.19

* All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

† Nitrogen by Kjeldahl. Compound nos. 5, 9 and 18 were first reduced with HI before digesting with H₂SO₄.

‡ Bromine by modified Stepnow's method.

TABLE 2. ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 3 : 5-DIBROMO SALICYLAMIDE AND ITS DERIVATIVES ZONE OF INHIBITION IN M.M. AT 100 µg/DISK CONCENTRATION

S.N.	Compound	Staph. aureus	Esch. coli	Proteus vulgaris	Kleb. aerogenes	S. typhi	Shig. dysenteriae
1.	3 : 5-dibromosalicylamide	—	10	20	—	—	—
2.	-n(3 : 5-dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-sulphanilamide	24	8	—	20	18	16
3.	n-(dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-o-sulphobenzoicimide	10	—	—	—	—	15
4.	n-(3 : 5-dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-salicylamide	—	10	—	—	10	8
5.	nm'-Methylene-bis-3 : 5-dibromosalicylamide	—	10	10	—	—	20

TABLE 3. ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF SOME 3 : 5-DIBROMO-SALICYLAMIDES

A = minimum inhibitory dose in ppm.

B = % spore germination at 200 ppm.

S.N.	Compound	A. niger	A. flavus	A. torius	Mucor mucido	Pen. not.	Fusar. elvic.	Rhz. nigr.	Trichod. sp.	
1.	3 : 5-dibromosalicylamide	A	250	200	200	150	150	200	150	200
		B	46	23	25	—	—	24	—	23
2.	Methylene-bis-3 : 5-dibromosalicylamide	A	200	150	150	150	150	200	100	—
		B	25	—	—	—	—	25	—	100
3.	N-(3 : 5-dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-salicylamide	A	250	200	200	200	150	250	150	250
		B	50	25	28	23	—	46	—	83
4.	N-(dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-naphthol	A	250	200	200	150	200	250	150	250
		B	46	21	18	—	21	43	—	47
5.	N-(dibromosalicylamidomethyl)-salicylic acid	A	250	200	200	200	250	250	150	—
		B	43	18	21	26	49	83	—	100

product appeared on dilution with cold water. Compound No. 1-9, 11, 12, 13, 17-23 were prepared by this method.

*Tscherniac Procedure*⁶ : Finely powdered reactive compound (0.02M) was dissolved slowly in conc. sulphuric acid and the N-hydroxymethyl-3,5-dibromosalicylamide (6.5 g, 0.02M) was added to it gradually under shaking and cooling. The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 2 days and then poured on crushed ice. The precipitated amidomethylated product was washed with water to remove sulphonated products and recrystallised from absolute alcohol or ligroin/benzene. In general Tscherniac procedure is more suitable for aromatic condensing compounds. Compound No. 10, 14, 15, 16 were prepared by this method.

Amidomethylation with 3,5-Dibromosalicylamide.

The amidomethylation products are given in the Table 1.

Antibacterial and Antimycotic activity of the various amidomethylation products have been studied on various Gram negative and Gram positive organisms viz., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas pyocyanea*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Streptococcus faecalis* and *Streptococcus pyogenes*.

A paper disc method⁷ was employed for the evaluation of the antibacterial activity⁷. The results of antibacterial and antimycotic activity of some of the selected compounds are given in Table 2 and 3.

Since these compounds are active at high concentration, they may not stand up in good stead to combat human ailments; however, they could safely be employed in plant diseases caused by bacteria/fungi, and as surface disinfectants in human pathology or veterinary practice.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. Hardas Singh, Professor and Head of Department of Microbiology, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, for providing facilities and guidance in microbiological screening.

References

1. Paper presented at the XVIII Indian Pharmaceutical Congress, held on the 28th December, 1966 at Bombay.
2. J. KIMMING, *Deutsch. Apoth. Zeit.*, 1971, 111, 1.
3. H. HELLMANN, *Newer Methods of Preparative Organic Chemistry*, Ed. W. Forst, Academic Press, New York, N.Y., 1963, Vol. II, p. 277.
4. H. E. ZATZG and W. B. MARTIN, *Organic Reactions*, 1965, 14, 52.
5. G. B. SINGH, *J. Indiana Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 1009.
6. G. B. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 262.
7. J. G. SCAUB, M. K. FOLEY, E. G. SCOTT and W. R. BAILEYN, *Diagnostic Microbiology*, C. V. Mosby & Co., 1958.